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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17101715>**Exosomes and Their Potential Use in Veterinary Medicine**

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Abstract: Currently, although exosomes are still predominantly investigated at the experimental level, rapid advancements in biotechnology, bioinformatics, and molecular biology are expected to facilitate their broader and more effective application in veterinary medicine in the near future. Applications of exosomes in veterinary practice are shaped according to species-specific pathologies; exosomes derived from various tissues offer targeted solutions in diagnostics, therapeutics, and regenerative medicine, thus laying the groundwork for personalized and optimized clinical approaches. However, physiological and immunological differences among species necessitate species-specific designs for exosome-based applications in veterinary medicine. Furthermore, for the widespread clinical adoption of these applications, establishing regulatory frameworks, completing long-term safety and efficacy studies, and standardizing application protocols are of critical importance. In conclusion, despite current limitations, exosomes hold considerable potential as therapeutic and diagnostic tools in veterinary medicine, and with support from interdisciplinary collaborations and advanced research, their integration into clinical practice is inevitable in the coming years.

1. Definition, Synthesis, and Properties of Exosomes

1.1. Definition and Properties of Exosomes

Exosomes are a subgroup of extracellular vesicles (EVs) released into the extracellular space by various cell types (Arraud et al, 2014). In recent years, these structures have received increasing attention in biomedical research due to their role in intercellular communication. Exosomes are formed by the release of intraluminal vesicles into the extracellular environment following the fusion of multivesicular bodies (MVBs), which are formed within the cell, with the plasma membrane (Pegtel and Gould, 2019; Han et al., 2022). These structures, which are secreted by most cell types through an endocytosis-derived mechanism, were first identified in reticulocytes in the 1980s (Clague and Urbé, 2010). Initially, exosomes were considered to be merely cellular waste products arising from cell damage or by-products of cellular homeostasis, without any significant functional impact on neighboring cells (Zhang et al., 2019). However, subsequent comprehensive studies have revealed that exosomes play an active role in intercellular communication and possess critical functions in various biological processes, including immune response, tumor progression, angiogenesis, and tissue regeneration (Théry et al., 2002).

Exosomes are EVs that can be secreted by nearly all cell types and are present in various biological fluids such as blood, urine, milk, and cerebrospinal fluid (Kalluri, 2016). Since exosomes reflect the biological characteristics of their cells of origin, their contents vary depending on the cell type, resulting in a highly heterogeneous structure (Pegtel and Gould, 2019; Smith et al., 2015). The heterogeneity of exosomes can be evaluated based on their size, cargo content, recipient cells, or the functional characteristics they exhibit depending on their cells of origin (Li et al, 2019). For instance, exosomes secreted by immune cells contain molecules that regulate immune responses, whereas those released from cancer cells may carry signals that promote tumor progression (Whiteside, 2016). This heterogeneity contributes to the diversity and specificity of the biological functions of exosomes.

Exosomes are EVs typically ranging from 30 to 150 nm in diameter and exhibit a spherical or cup-shaped morphology (Théry et al., 2006). Their small size enables them to easily cross biological membranes, making them effective mediators of long-distance intercellular signaling. The small size and characteristic morphology of exosomes prevent their rapid clearance by the mononuclear phagocyte system, allowing them to remain in circulation for extended periods; this enables them to play critical roles in intercellular communication. These structural and functional characteristics significantly enhance the potential of exosomes to be utilized as delivery systems or diagnostic tools in biomedical applications (Villarroya-Beltri et al., 2014).

Exosomes are surrounded by a lipid bilayer membrane, which is derived from the plasma membrane of their cell of origin. The lipids forming this membrane are rich in molecules such as cholesterol, sphingolipids, and phosphatidylserine. This high lipid content helps exosomes remain more stable in biological fluids (Zhang et al., 2019). On the surface of the exosome membrane, there are tetraspanin proteins (CD9, CD63, CD81), integrins, and target cell-specific marker proteins. These proteins play a crucial role in the recognition of exosomes and their interaction with target cells (Mathivanan et al., 2010; Raposo and Stoorvogel, 2013).

Exosomes are rich in proteins, nucleic acids, and lipids. Among their protein components are TSG101 and Alix, which are involved in multivesicular body formation, heat shock proteins (HSP60, HSP70, HSP90), and cytoskeletal proteins such as actin and tubulin (Théry et al., 2006). Their nucleic acid content can include mRNA, miRNAs, long non-coding RNAs (lncRNAs), and even DNA fragments (Valadi et al., 2007). These molecules support the ability of exosomes to modulate gene expression in recipient cells (Zhang et al., 2019).

The density of exosomes ranges between 1.13 and 1.19 g/mL, a property that allows them to be isolated using ultracentrifugation techniques (Théry et al., 2018). Additionally, their ability to remain stable in biological fluids for extended periods enhances their potential use as drug and gene delivery systems in clinical applications (Alvarez-Erviti et al., 2011).

1.2. Biological Functions of Exosomes

Exosomes are heterogeneous EVs whose characteristics vary depending on their cellular origin and molecular cargo. They play critical roles in numerous physiological and pathological processes. Among their primary functions are the facilitation of intercellular communication and genetic material transfer, modulation of immune responses, promotion of tissue repair and regenerative mechanisms, maintenance of cellular homeostasis, and regulation of key biological events such as cell growth, development, and differentiation (Chung et al., 2020a,b).

Exosomes play a critical role in intercellular communication by transferring molecular messages from donor cells to recipient cells, utilizing various mechanisms to fulfill this function. These mechanisms include direct signal transmission via surface ligands, the transfer of active receptors to target cells, and epigenetic reprogramming through functional molecules. Valadi et al. (2007) demonstrated that exosomes are capable of carrying genetic materials such as mRNA and miRNA, thereby influencing gene expression in recipient cells. Through this capability, exosomes effectively function as a “cellular postal service.” This communication mechanism plays a pivotal role in various biological contexts, including the transfer of antigenic information among immune cells and the manipulation of the tumor microenvironment by cancer cells (Raposo and Stoorvogel, 2013).

Exosomes play both immunostimulatory and immunosuppressive roles within the immune system. Exosomes secreted by dendritic cells can enhance immune responses by activating T cells through antigen presentation (Théry et al., 2009). Additionally, exosomes released from other immune cells, such as macrophages and β -cells, are involved in the propagation or suppression of inflammatory signals. For instance, Whiteside (2016) reported that tumor-derived exosomes can suppress the immune system, thereby promoting tumor progression.

Exosomes derived from mesenchymal stem cells (MSCs) support tissue repair through the delivery of anti-inflammatory cytokines and growth factors (Ratajczak et al., 2006). Lai et al. (2010) experimentally demonstrated that MSC-derived exosomes reduce myocardial ischemia/reperfusion injury and promote cardiac tissue regeneration. Similarly, Zhang et al. (2015) reported that exosomes accelerate the healing of chronic wounds.

Exosomes play both beneficial and detrimental roles in various diseases. Despite advancements in diagnostic and therapeutic strategies, including surgery, radiation, and chemotherapy, the development of novel, more effective, and less toxic anticancer agents remains a critical area of research (Bilici et al., 2025). In cancer progression, tumor-derived exosomes carry signals that promote metastasis and play a critical role in reshaping the tumor microenvironment (Peinado et al., 2012). For example, exosomes originating from melanoma have been reported to direct bone marrow progenitor cells toward a metastatic phenotype. In neurodegenerative diseases, exosomes contribute to disease progression by facilitating the intercellular spread of pathological proteins, such as beta-amyloid peptides in Alzheimer’s disease (Rajendran et al., 2006). These findings suggest that exosomes act as a “double-edged sword” in the context of disease processes.

Exosomes have emerged as potential delivery systems for the treatment of neurological disorders due to their ability to cross physiological barriers such as the blood-brain barrier. It has been experimentally demonstrated that siRNA molecules delivered to the brain via

exosomes can induce gene silencing effects (Alvarez-Erviti et al., 2011). Furthermore, in cancer therapy, the use of exosomes to deliver chemotherapeutic agents to target tissues holds promise for enhancing therapeutic efficacy while reducing side effects (Kamerkar et al., 2017).

Exosomes regulate cell differentiation and tissue organization during critical processes such as embryogenesis and tissue development through the signaling molecules they carry. For instance, exosomes secreted by stem cells have been reported to contain miRNAs that determine cell fate, thereby transmitting developmental signals to target cells (Ratajczak et al., 2006). This finding indicates that exosomes play an active role not only in adult tissues but also in embryonic development processes.

1.3. Biomedical Potential of Exosomes

Exosomes possess significant potential for therapeutic applications due to their biological functions and their capacity to deliver bioactive molecules in a target-specific manner. Critical obstacles to cancer treatment are drug insensitivity and resistance (Bilici and Akkoç, 2025). Their high bioavailability and low immunogenicity make them a more effective alternative compared to conventional drug delivery systems. These features position exosomes as innovative tools in the biomedical field, offering broad therapeutic opportunities, particularly in cancer treatment, management of neurodegenerative diseases, and tissue regeneration (Gurunathan et al., 2021; Zhang et al., 2015).

In regenerative medicine, exosome-based therapies are being developed to repair damaged tissues. Preclinical studies have demonstrated the efficacy of exosomes in burn treatment and chronic wound healing (Zhang et al., 2015). In cancer therapy, exosomes can be utilized for targeted delivery of chemotherapeutic agents, thereby reducing side effects while enhancing treatment efficacy (Kamerkar et al., 2017). In neurological diseases, exosomes show promising potential as both biomarkers and therapeutic tools. Specifically, pathological proteins carried by exosomes in diseases such as Alzheimer's and Parkinson's may serve as important indicators for early diagnosis (Goetzl et al., 2015). Additionally, in the field of food science, the role of exosomes in the delivery of bioactive compounds is being investigated. This approach offers the potential to improve the efficacy of molecules with low bioavailability (Mu et al., 2014).

2. Biogenesis of Exosomes

The biogenesis of exosomes is a multi-step process involving the coordinated progression of cellular mechanisms. This process begins with the invagination of the plasma membrane and continues with the formation of early endosomes. Intraluminal vesicles (ILVs) are generated by inward budding within early endosomes, and the aggregation of these structures leads to the formation of MVBs (Bobrie et al., 2011; Minciacchi et al., 2015). Unlike other EVs such as microvesicles, exosome biogenesis is characterized by inward budding and mechanisms specific to endosomal pathways.

2.1. Formation of Early Endosomes

The initiation of exosome biogenesis involves the formation of early endosomes through endocytosis of the plasma membrane. At this stage, proteins, lipids, and other molecules on the cell surface are internalized via clathrin-dependent or clathrin-independent endocytic pathways (Harding et al., 1983). Early endosomes serve as sorting hubs for the internalized content. While some molecules are recycled back to the plasma membrane via recycling endosomes, others are directed to form late endosomes (Théry et al., 2002).

2.2. Maturation to Late Endosomes and Formation of Intraluminal Vesicles

Early endosomes mature into late endosomes, which are also referred to as MVBs. Within MVBs, intraluminal vesicles (ILVs) are present; these ILVs serve as precursors to exosomes (Kowal et al., 2014). The formation of ILVs occurs through the inward budding of the endosomal membrane. Unlike microvesicles, which bud outward from the plasma membrane, this process reflects the internal dynamics of the endosomal system (Hessvik and Llorente, 2018).

2.3. Transport and Fate Determination of MVBs

After formation, MVBs can follow two distinct intracellular pathways: (1) fusion with lysosomes leading to degradation of their contents, or (2) fusion with the plasma membrane resulting in the release of exosomes into the extracellular space (Théry et al., 2018). This fate determination is regulated by Rab GTPase proteins. For instance, Rab27a and Rab27b promote the transport of MVBs to the plasma membrane and subsequent exosome secretion (Ostrowski et al., 2010). Conversely, Rab7 is involved in directing MVBs toward lysosomal degradation (Vanlandingham and Ceresa, 2009). Cellular cholesterol levels also influence this decision; low cholesterol favors lysosomal fusion, whereas high cholesterol promotes exosome release. During the secretion process, SNARE proteins regulate the fusion mechanism (Ostrowski et al., 2010).

3. Exosome Isolation Methods

Exosomes are isolated from biological fluids such as blood, urine, saliva, cerebrospinal fluid, or from cell culture supernatants. Isolation methods rely on the physical properties (size, density) and biochemical characteristics (surface proteins) of exosomes (Théry et al., 2018). The heterogeneous nature of biological samples—such as protein aggregates, lipoproteins, or other EVs—complicates isolation. Therefore, methods are optimized based on purity, yield, cost, and the intended application (Kalluri and LeBleu, 2020).

3.1. Differential Ultracentrifugation

Differential ultracentrifugation is the most commonly used traditional method for exosome isolation and is considered the "gold standard" (Théry et al., 2006). This method relies on differences in sedimentation rates of particles. Low-speed centrifugation ($2,000\text{--}10,000 \times g$) is used to remove cell debris and large particles. Exosomes are pelleted by high-speed ultracentrifugation, typically at $100,000\text{--}120,000 \times g$ for 1–2 hours (Li et al., 2017).

3.2. Density Gradient Centrifugation

Density gradient centrifugation uses gradient materials such as sucrose or iodixanol to separate exosomes based on their density differences (Tauro et al., 2012). As an extension of differential ultracentrifugation, exosomes (with densities ranging from 1.13 to 1.19 g/mL) are separated from other particles. This method allows for the collection of exosomes released from MVBs within specific density bands (Théry et al., 2006).

3.3. Size-Based Isolation Techniques

Size-based methods target the nanometer-scale size of exosomes (30–150 nm). Size exclusion chromatography (SEC) separates samples by passing them through a porous matrix, fractionating exosomes based on size (Böing et al., 2014). SEC preserves the biological activity of exosomes and provides high purity. Exosomes can also be concentrated by ultrafiltration using molecular weight cutoff filters (e.g., 10–100 kDa) (Cheruvanky et al., 2007). This method is rapid and cost-effective; however, membrane clogging and exosome loss may occur. While

size-based methods offer simplicity and speed, they carry the risk of co-isolating lipoproteins or other nanoparticles (Li et al., 2017).

3.4. Immunoaffinity Capture

Immunoaffinity capture employs antibodies targeting specific proteins on the exosome surface, such as tetraspanins CD63, CD9, and CD81 (Escola et al., 1998). Exosomes are captured using magnetic beads, microfluidic devices, or solid-phase supports. This method provides high specificity for isolating distinct exosome subpopulations (Chen et al., 2010).

3.5. Polymer-Based Precipitation

Polymer-based precipitation uses water-soluble polymers like polyethylene glycol (PEG) to precipitate exosomes by altering their solubility (Rider et al., 2016). After incubation with PEG, samples are centrifuged at low speed to pellet the exosomes. Commercial kits, such as ExoQuick, have popularized this method (Helwa et al., 2017).

3.6. Microfluidic Technologies

Microfluidic devices represent an innovative approach for exosome isolation by combining size, density, or immunoaffinity principles at a microscale (Chen et al., 2010). These systems separate exosomes using acoustic waves, electrophoresis, or antibody-coated surfaces. For example, Lee et al. (2015) demonstrated rapid and efficient exosome isolation using a microfluidic device.

3.7. Other Methods

Flow Cytometry Sorting: Exosomes can be separated by fluorescent labeling of surface markers, although this method is primarily used for analytical purposes (Nolte-'t Hoen et al., 2012). Dielectrophoresis: Exosome isolation using electric fields, though not yet widely adopted (Ibsen et al., 2017).

4. Application of Exosomes in Clinical Therapies

Exosomes have recently emerged as promising biological tools in clinical therapeutic approaches due to their intrinsic biological carrier capacity, targetability, and low immunogenicity (Kalluri and LeBleu, 2020; Alvarez-Erviti et al., 2011). Their cell-derived and biologically compatible nature makes them a safe and effective treatment option. Exosome-based applications show great potential in both experimental and clinical research, particularly in fields such as regenerative medicine, oncology, neurological disorders, and immune modulation. The ability of exosomes to cross physiological barriers and deliver biomolecules to target tissues has positioned them as strategic biotherapeutic agents in many clinical treatment areas today (Qu et al., 2018; Valadi et al., 2007).

Exosomes derived from MSCs play a crucial role in tissue repair and regeneration in regenerative medicine, owing to their carried growth factors (e.g., VEGF), anti-inflammatory cytokines, and miRNAs (Ratajczak et al., 2012). MSC-derived exosomes have been shown to accelerate healing and support cellular regeneration in various tissues such as the heart, liver, nervous system, skin, and musculoskeletal system (Lai et al., 2010; Zhang et al., 2015). Due to these properties, exosomes offer an innovative and cell-free alternative for the treatment of many chronic tissue injuries, especially musculoskeletal disorders in veterinary medicine (Mocchi et al., 2020). El-Tookhy et al. (2017) demonstrated that treating experimentally induced wounds in dogs with exosomal fluid accelerated healing and improved wound quality compared to controls, highlighting the safety and efficacy of exosome therapy.

The ability of exosomes to cross the blood-brain barrier makes them highly valuable in the treatment of neurodegenerative diseases. Exosomes also show promise in acute neurological

events such as stroke. Xin et al. (2013) reported that exosomes derived from MSCs support neurogenesis and functional recovery following stroke. These findings suggest that exosomes can play an active role not only as carriers but also as therapeutic agents. In this regard, exosomes have the potential to be used as targeted gene or drug delivery systems in diseases such as Parkinson's, Alzheimer's, and similar disorders. Moreover, exosomes are also indicated to be useful not only as carriers of therapeutic molecules but also in the identification of disease biomarkers. Exosomes released from neuronal cells carry disease-specific proteins, making them suitable for evaluation via liquid biopsy methods for early diagnosis (Rajendran et al., 2006).

In the field of veterinary neurology, research on the use of exosomes as both diagnostic and therapeutic tools in conditions such as epilepsy, traumatic brain injury, and spinal cord lesions is increasing. In this respect, exosomes are becoming an important part of translational medicine not only in human healthcare but also in animal health. In animals with spinal cord injury, stem cell-derived exosomes reduced pro-inflammatory factors (TNF- α , IL-1 β) and the apoptotic protein BAX, increased anti-inflammatory cytokines (IL-10, IL-4), and enhanced motor function (Zhang et al., 2022).

Exosomes play an active role in cancer biology, particularly in tumor development and metastasis processes. These small vesicles secreted by tumor cells reshape the tumor microenvironment by carrying biological signals that support tumor progression and metastasis (Peinado et al., 2012). Kulka et al. (2022) reported that dogs with diffuse large B-cell lymphoma and adenocarcinoma exhibited increased numbers but decreased sizes of plasma exosomes. Żmigrodzka et al. (2019) found that dogs with various types of cancer showed an increased number of platelet-, leukocyte-, and T cell-derived EVs. Similarly, in a study conducted by Troyer et al. (2017), it was demonstrated that osteosarcoma cells secrete exosomes with tumor-promoting properties that act on circulating T cells obtained from healthy dogs. These exosomes were reported to suppress immune responses by inhibiting T cell activation and proliferation. On the other hand, although exosomes derived from osteoblasts also exhibit immunosuppressive effects, this effect was found to be less pronounced compared to those derived from osteosarcoma cells.

Recent research has demonstrated that exosomes, beyond their role in regulating fundamental cellular functions, possess significant potential for diagnostic and therapeutic applications in the field of veterinary medicine. Brady et al. (2018) explored the potential of exosomes as diagnostic biomarkers for canine osteosarcoma. Their study involved a comparative proteomic analysis of serum-derived exosomes from three groups: dogs diagnosed with osteosarcoma, those with traumatic fractures, and healthy controls. The findings indicated that proteomic profiling of exosomal cargo could effectively differentiate osteosarcoma cases from healthy individuals. Additionally, this method showed promise in helping to rule out the presence of pulmonary metastases. Weinman et al. (2021) reported that the exosomal protein profile can serve as a prognostic marker to predict chemotherapeutic outcomes in appendicular osteosarcoma. Garnica et al. (2020) reported that serum exosome numbers and exosomal miRNA content have high potential as chemotherapeutic prognostic indicators in dogs with multicentric lymphoma. Fish et al. (2018) demonstrated that canine mammary tumor (CMT) cells also release exosomes, similar to human breast cancer tumors. They reported that these exosomes could be used as biomarkers. Additionally, miRNA expression was detected in the exosomes, with the presence of specific miRNAs such as miR-18a, miR-19a, and miR-181a being particularly noted. It was emphasized that these exosomes play an important role in cell proliferation, tumor formation, and cancer progression. Asada et al., (2019) reported that although the core RNA and protein contents of exosomes derived from canine lymphoid tumor cell lines were similar, their miRNA profiles differed among the cell lines. Notably, they

highlighted that the levels of certain miRNAs—such as miR-151, miR-8908a-3p, and miR-486—as well as the presence of CD82 protein varied between exosomes derived from vincristine-sensitive and vincristine-resistant cell lines. Urine contains exosomes shed by urothelial cells, making urinary exosome-derived miRNAs promising biomarkers for renal, bladder, urethral, and prostate diseases. Ichii et al., (2018) profiled urinary exosomal miRNAs in dogs and cats, identifying specific miRNAs—such as miR-26a and miR-10a/b in dogs, and let-7b, miR-22, and miR-26a in cats—that were significantly altered in early kidney disease and correlated with renal function or site-specific kidney damage. These findings suggest that urinary exosome-derived miRNAs may serve as novel diagnostic tools in veterinary medicine, though further studies are needed before clinical application (Diomaiuto et al., 2021).

Due to their inherent biological origin and low immunogenicity, exosomes have emerged as effective targeted delivery vehicles, particularly in combination chemo- and immunotherapeutic strategies. Their surfaces can be engineered to display target-specific ligands, thereby enhancing their specificity toward diseased tissues. Notably, exosomes that are genetically or biochemically modified to carry tumor-specific cargo facilitate the selective transport of therapeutic agents to tumor sites. This targeted delivery approach not only minimizes systemic toxicity but also maximizes the accumulation of therapeutic molecules within malignant tissues, thereby significantly improving overall treatment efficacy (Tian et al., 2014). Howard et al., (2020) investigated feline mammary adenocarcinoma (FMA) and reported that while the role of exosomes in FMA remains unclear, they may be associated with chemotherapy resistance.

In addition, exosomes have been reported to hold significant potential in the development of cancer vaccines. Their ability to carry tumor-associated antigens and stimulate immune responses renders them valuable candidates for immunotherapeutic applications (Ichim et al., 2008). Emerging evidence suggests that exosomes may function not only as delivery vehicles but also as bioactive agents capable of activating the immune system (Xu et al., 2020; Choi et al., 2020; Zhang et al., 2023).

In veterinary oncology, particularly in canine and feline tumor models, the efficacy of exosome-based therapies has been investigated. It has been reported that exosomes derived from CTVT (Canine Transmissible Venereal Tumor) can serve as an antigen source for dendritic cells, and that these cells may exert potential therapeutic effects when administered to dogs (Ramos-Zayas et al., 2018). In particular, exosomes obtained from venereal tumors, when administered intravenously, were shown to stimulate immune responses in dogs and induce therapeutic effects. This field holds significant potential both for enhancing therapeutic efficacy and minimizing adverse effects. Consequently, exosomes provide an innovative platform in oncological treatments, serving as biomarkers and targets to inhibit disease progression, as well as enabling the effective and safe delivery of therapeutic agents.

Exosomes released from both pathogen sources and host cells play a significant role in modulating the immune response during the course of infection (Schorey and Harding, 2016). Particularly in viral, bacterial, and parasitic infections, exosomes exhibit bidirectional functions: while in some instances they facilitate the spread of infection, in others they can either stimulate or suppress the immune response (Saad et al., 2021). Exosomes from infected cells can serve as biomarkers for viral infections. In cats with calicivirus-positive chronic gingivostomatitis, adipose-derived MSCs produced more exosomes than in healthy cats, which displayed a distinct protein profile: eight proteins were unique to infected cats, while 13 proteins were downregulated and 17 were upregulated (Chaudhari et al., 2022; Villatoro et al., 2020). Bovine milk exosomal miRNAs, including bta-miRNA-223, miRNA-142-5p, miRNA-378, and bta-miRNA-185, show altered expression following *Staphylococcus aureus* infection, and bta-

miRNA-223-3p is upregulated in subclinical mastitis, highlighting the diagnostic potential of milk exosomes for mastitis (Heidarpour et al., 2024).

Exosomes also hold considerable potential in antiviral and antibacterial therapies. For instance, exosomes derived from immune cells can carry antiviral molecules such as interferons, thereby inhibiting viral replication (Khatua et al., 2009). Certain viruses, such as HIV and Epstein-Barr virus (EBV), have been shown to exploit the exosomal pathway to facilitate the transfer of viral RNA and proteins from infected to uninfected cells, contributing to the spread of infection and enhancing viral pathogenicity (Meckes and Raab-Traub, 2011). On the other hand, these exosomes can contribute to the activation of immune cells, thereby enhancing antiviral responses. In chronic infections such as tuberculosis, exosomes released from macrophages have been shown to carry bacterial antigens, which can stimulate T cells and modulate the host immune response (Bhatnagar et al., 2007).

Exosomes derived from MSCs exert immunoregulatory effects by delivering anti-inflammatory cytokines such as IL-10 and immunomodulatory miRNAs (Ratajczak et al., 2012). In models of rheumatoid arthritis, MSC-derived exosomes have been shown to reduce inflammation and joint damage (Chen et al., 2018), while in inflammatory bowel disease, they promote mucosal healing (Mao et al., 2016). Similarly, their therapeutic effects have been demonstrated in experimental models of multiple sclerosis and other autoimmune disorders (Li et al., 2018). In addition to their therapeutic applications, exosomes are also being explored as diagnostic tools. The molecular contents of exosomes present in biological fluids can serve as non-invasive biomarkers for monitoring disease activity and treatment response (Mittelbrunn and Sánchez-Madrid, 2012). In conclusion, exosomes offer innovative potential as both therapeutic agents and diagnostic tools in inflammatory and autoimmune diseases.

In veterinary medicine, exosomes are being developed as non-invasive diagnostic tools for infectious diseases due to the specific biomarkers they carry. Moreover, their immunomodulatory properties offer therapeutic potential for controlling infection-induced inflammation.

Lee and Saadeldin (2020) reviewed the properties of canine EVs and concluded that EV-associated miRNAs are present in oviductal fluid, suggesting a role in regulating oocyte maturation. Supporting this, a recent study showed that treating cat sperm with oviductal-derived exosomes enhanced sperm motility (Ferraz et al., 2019). Qamar et al., (2019) hypothesized that supplementation with exosomes from canine adipose-derived mesenchymal stem cells (Ad-MSCs) could repair sperm damaged by the freezing process. Although post-thaw motility and live sperm percentages were not significantly different from controls, exosome-treated sperm showed higher rates of intact plasma and acrosome membranes, along with significantly improved motility and viability.

5. Diseases and Applications of Exosomes in Cats and Dogs

5.1. Chronic Kidney Disease (CKD)

CKD is a common condition in cats and geriatric dogs, with conventional treatments primarily addressing symptoms. MSC-derived exosomes have demonstrated potential to reduce inflammation and promote regeneration in renal tissue. Quimby et al. (2021) reported that intravenous administration of MSC-derived exosomes in cats improved renal function parameters, such as creatinine levels, and suppressed inflammatory cytokines. In canine experimental models, exosomes have been observed to attenuate renal fibrosis and repair glomerular damage (Nagaishi et al., 2016). Administration is typically performed via systemic (intravenous) injection, whereby exosomes target renal tissue to exert localized therapeutic effects.

5.2. Osteoarthritis and Joint Diseases

Osteoarthritis is a common age-related joint disease in dogs and is increasingly recognized in cats. MSC-derived exosomes have chondroprotective and anti-inflammatory properties, offering potential for cartilage preservation and pain alleviation. Saulnier et al. (2020) demonstrated that intra-articular injection of exosomes in a canine osteoarthritis model reduced synovial inflammation and improved joint function. Although experimental studies in cats are limited, similar mechanisms are suggested to be effective (Zhang et al., 2019). Exosomes are typically administered via direct intra-articular injection, providing localized therapeutic effects.

5.3. Inflammatory Bowel Disease (IBD)

IBD in cats and dogs is characterized by chronic gastrointestinal symptoms. MSC-derived exosomes show promise in the treatment of IBD by suppressing inflammation in the intestinal mucosa and promoting epithelial barrier repair. Wu et al. (2022) reported that oral or intravenous administration of exosomes in canine IBD models improved intestinal permeability and reduced pro-inflammatory cytokines such as TNF- α . In feline cases, MSC-derived exosomes were observed to support intestinal homeostasis and alleviate clinical symptoms (Kang and Guo, 2019). These treatments are typically administered via systemic or local (oral) routes.

5.4. Dermatological Diseases

Chronic skin diseases, such as atopic dermatitis, are common in cats and dogs and are often associated with immune dysregulation. MSC-derived exosomes may be effective in these conditions by promoting skin regeneration and modulating immune responses. Yang et al. (2021) reported that topical application of exosomes in a canine atopic dermatitis model improved skin barrier function and reduced pruritus. In cats, the anti-inflammatory effects of exosomes in the treatment of allergic dermatitis are currently being investigated experimentally (Villani et al., 2023). Topical administration is typically performed via direct spraying onto the skin surface or in cream formulations.

5.5. Neurological Diseases

Neurological disorders represent significant causes of morbidity in cats (e.g., feline epilepsy) and dogs (e.g., degenerative myelopathy). The ability of exosomes to cross the blood-brain barrier offers therapeutic potential in these diseases. Kornicka et al. (2019) demonstrated that intravenous administration of MSC-derived exosomes in a canine spinal cord injury model supported neuronal repair and improved motor functions. In cats, the experimental use of exosomes for the treatment of neuroinflammatory conditions has shown promising results (Quimby et al., 2021). Typically, the application is performed via systemic injection, enabling exosomes to reach and exert effects on brain tissue.

5.6. Cardiovascular Diseases

Cardiovascular diseases, such as dilated cardiomyopathy, are prevalent in dogs, whereas hypertrophic cardiomyopathy is commonly observed in cats. MSC-derived exosomes have demonstrated potential therapeutic effects in these conditions by promoting angiogenesis within cardiac tissue and mitigating inflammatory damage. Li et al. (2020) reported that administration of exosomes significantly improved cardiac function and attenuated fibrosis in a canine myocardial infarction model. Although data regarding feline models remain limited, analogous beneficial effects have been proposed (Saulnier et al., 2020). Typically, exosomes are delivered via intravenous or intracardiac injection routes.

Exosomes have potential applications not only as therapeutic tools but also as biomarkers in cats and dogs. The study by Yang et al. (2017) demonstrated that exosomal miRNAs can distinguish dogs with MMVD (myxomatous mitral valve disease) and concurrent CHF (chronic heart failure) from healthy controls. In this study, exosomal miRNA profiles were compared with total plasma miRNAs, and alterations in the expression of cfa-miR-9, cfa-miR-181c, cfa-miR-495, and cfa-miR-599 were found to be associated with both disease progression and age. These findings support the potential use of exosomal miRNAs as valuable biomarkers for different stages of disease. Beaumier et al., (2020) demonstrated that changes in EV-miRNAs in dogs receiving doxorubicin could serve as strong early biomarkers for DOX-induced cardiotoxicity and guide the choice of treatment and cardioprotective strategies.

6. Exosome Therapy in Horses: Novel Approaches

Exosome therapy presents a promising approach for the treatment of orthopedic, inflammatory, respiratory, and reproductive system diseases in horses. Due to their anti-inflammatory effects, capacity to support tissue regeneration, and minimally invasive administration methods, exosomes offer a valuable alternative to conventional therapies. Joint osteoarthritis and tendon injuries (such as tendinitis and tendinosis) are common conditions observed in racehorses and sport horses (Jammes et al., 2023). In horses with osteoarthritis, mesenchymal stem cell-derived exosomes have demonstrated anti-inflammatory and regenerative effects, contributing to the repair of cartilage tissue and presenting a potential alternative to conventional treatment options. Specifically, in equine models, bone marrow mesenchymal stem cell (BM-MSC)-derived EVs have been shown to significantly suppress IL-1 β -induced inflammatory mediators in chondrocytes (O'Brien et al., 2023). When evaluated in terms of reproductive system diseases, bone marrow-derived exosomes have demonstrated therapeutic potential in the treatment of chronic endometritis in Arabian mares (Abdelnaby et al., 2024). Collectively, these findings suggest that exosome therapy represents a minimally invasive and innovative treatment option in equine health, supporting tissue regeneration and modulation of inflammation.

Exosome therapy in equine medicine is gaining increasing attention, particularly for enhancing the performance of racehorses and accelerating their recovery processes. Studies conducted in horses have observed that intra-articular injection of MSC-derived exosomes promotes the proliferation of cartilage cells (chondrocytes) and reduces inflammation. Additionally, in cases of tendon injuries, exosomes have been reported to accelerate tendon cell regeneration and decrease fibrosis.

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